

Assessment of Anxiety and Depression Beyond the Postpartum Period Among Tunisian Women

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Abstract

Background: Pregnancy induces significant hormonal, immunological, and psychological changes, increasing the risk of anxiety and depression. While perinatal mental health has been studied during pregnancy and the immediate postpartum period, data on long-term psychological effects remain limited.

Objectives: This study aimed to describe Tunisian women with at least one full-term pregnancy and assess the long-term impact of pregnancy on mental health using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS).

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in April 2025 including 36 Tunisian women aged ≥ 18 years, at least six weeks postpartum. Participants completed a bilingual (French/Arabic) online questionnaire covering sociodemographic, obstetric, and mental health information. Anxiety and depression symptoms were assessed with HADS, and associations with clinical and sociodemographic factors were analyzed.

Results: The mean age was 30.3 ± 5.6 years. Mean HADS scores indicated mild to moderate symptoms (anxiety: 8.8 ± 3.7 ; depression: 8.5 ± 3.2). Moderate to severe anxiety and depression were more frequent among women from rural areas, with higher education, unwanted pregnancies, emergency cesarean sections, or postpartum complications. Breastfeeding was less common among symptomatic women, though not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Longitudinal studies are needed to better understand postpartum mental health trajectories and optimize maternal care.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Postpartum, Tunisian women, HADS, Mental health

Introduction

Pregnancy is a complex physiological process that induces significant endocrine, immunological, and psychological changes in women (1). These transformations can profoundly affect mental health, making pregnant and postpartum women particularly vulnerable to anxiety and depressive disorders (2,3). Hormonal fluctuations—particularly in estrogen, progesterone, and cortisol—may disrupt emotional regulation and contribute to the onset of psychiatric symptoms (4,5).

According to international studies, depressive disorders affect approximately 7% to 15% of women during pregnancy (6,7), while postpartum depression impacts 10% to 20% of women in the weeks or months following childbirth (8). These conditions represent major complications, with serious consequences for the mother, the newborn, and the family. However, such disorders often go underdiagnosed due to symptom overlap with common physiological changes of pregnancy and the postpartum period, such as fatigue, sleep disturbances, and appetite changes (9).

Beyond the immediate postpartum phase, some studies suggest that anxiety and depressive symptoms may persist or even emerge long after delivery, potentially leading to lasting impairments in women's quality of life (10). This chronicity may be influenced by various psychosocial factors, including parenting stress, lack of social support, or a preexisting but unrecognized psychiatric vulnerability (11).

Given these findings, psychological monitoring during and after pregnancy is a public health priority. The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), developed by Zigmond and Snaith in 1983, is a widely used and validated tool for screening anxiety and depression in both hospital and community settings (12). Its reliability has been confirmed in perinatal populations (13). However, despite growing awareness of perinatal mental health, few studies have specifically examined the long-term psychological impact of past pregnancies. Most existing research focuses primarily on the immediate perinatal period, leaving a gap in the understanding of mental health outcomes further postpartum (14).

Objectives

This study aims to:

- Describe the characteristics of the study population;
- Assess the long-term impact of pregnancy on women's mental health using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS).

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in April 2025 among Tunisian women aged 18 years and older who had experienced at least one full-term pregnancy (≥ 37 weeks gestation) and had delivered at least six weeks prior to enrollment. A total of 36 participants were included.

Women were excluded if they were currently pregnant, had a history of diagnosed psychiatric disorders prior to pregnancy (e.g., major depressive disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, bipolar disorder), had experienced recent perinatal loss, or declined to participate.

Data were collected between April 1 and April 30, 2025, using a self-administered questionnaire available in both French and Arabic. The questionnaire was distributed online via social media platforms, primarily Facebook, with weekly reminders. It gathered information on sociodemographic characteristics, medical and obstetric history, details of the most recent pregnancy and delivery, and current mental health status.

Mental health was assessed using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), a validated instrument composed of 14 items equally divided to assess anxiety (HADS-A) and depression (HADS-D). Scores of 0–7 indicate no symptoms, 8–10 suggest borderline cases, and 11 or higher indicate probable clinical anxiety or depression.

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations or medians with interquartile ranges, depending on the distribution. All participants provided informed consent, and the study was conducted in accordance with ethical research standards.

Results

A total of 36 participants were included in the study. The mean age was 30.25 ± 5.59 years (range: 24–44). Twenty-one participants (58.3%) resided in rural areas.

Regarding employment status, 63% were unemployed. The mean body mass index (BMI) was 28.91 ± 3.3 kg/m², with 47.2% of participants having a BMI greater than 30 kg/m². A higher education level was observed in 80.5% of participants (n = 29).

The median gravidity was 1 (range: 1–7), median parity was 0 (0–4), and median number of abortions was 0 (0–4)

Eight participants had a history of gynecological surgery (Figure 1), and four reported infertility, with a median duration of 4 years (2–8). A scarred uterus was noted in 33.3% of participants (n = 12). **(Figure 1)**

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to history of gynecological surgery

Additionally, 36.1% had medical or surgical comorbidities, including hypertension (30.8%), diabetes mellitus (23.1%), anemia (23.1%), and dyslipidemia (15.4%) (Table II).

Table I: Distribution of participants according to medical history

Antécédents personnels	Effectif (n)	Pourcentage (%)
Hypertension artérielle	4	30,8
Diabète	3	23,1
Anémie	3	23,1
Dyslipidémie	2	15,4
Autres	1	7,6
Total	13	100

All pregnancies were spontaneous. Gestational diabetes was diagnosed in two participants. All participants received prenatal care from a specialist obstetrician. Thirty-five deliveries occurred at term, with one preterm birth (<37 weeks gestation). Cesarean section was performed in 19 participants, five of whom had pathological fetal heart rate tracings.

The mean anxiety score (HADS-A) was 8.8 ± 3.7 (range : 0–21), and the mean depression score (HADS-D) was 8.5 ± 3.2 (range: 1–17) (Figure 2, Figure 3).

Figure 2: Distribution of the study population according to anxiety symptomatology

Figure 3: Distribution of the study population according to depressive symptomatology

Factors Influencing Mental Health

Anxiety

Moderate to severe anxiety was significantly more prevalent among participants from rural areas (69.5% vs 56.9%, $p = 0.041$), those with higher education levels (71.7% vs 84.7%, $p = 0.049$), in cases of unwanted pregnancy (30.4% vs 16.9%, $p = 0.034$), emergency cesarean section (71.7% vs 45.8%, $p = 0.001$), and postpartum complications (21.7% vs 10.2%, $p = 0.027$) (Table III).

Tableau II : Factors influencing anxiety symptoms

Variables	Anxiété absente ou faible (HADS-A \leq 10)	Moderate to severe anxiety (HADS-A score $>$ 10)	P value
Mean age (years)	29,5 \pm 5,8	28,9 \pm 6,4	0,64
Residence			
Urban (%)	43,1	30,4	0,041
Rural (%)	56,9	69,6	
Higher education (%)	84,7	71,7	0,049
Unwanted pregnancy (%)	16,9	30,4	0,034
Emergency cesarean (%)	45,8	71,7	0,001
Postpartum complication (%)	10,2	21,7	0,027
Exclusive breastfeeding (%)	67,8	43,5	0,055

Depression

Similarly, moderate to severe depression was more frequent among rural participants (72.7% vs 55.9%, $p = 0.035$), those with higher education levels (63.6% vs 84.7%, $p = 0.003$), unwanted pregnancies (36.4% vs 17%, $p = 0.005$), emergency cesarean section (72.7% vs 47.5%, $p = 0.009$), and postpartum complications (27.3% vs 10.2%, $p = 0.006$) (Table IV).

Tableau III : Factors influencing depressive symptoms

Variables	No/Minimal Depression	Moderate to Severe Depression	P value
Mean age (years)	29,7 ± 5,9	28.5 ± 6.4	0,320
residence			
Urban (%)	44,1	27,3	0,035
Rural (%)	55,9	72,7	
Higher education (%)	84,7	63,6	0,003
Unwanted pregnancy (%)	17,0	36,4	0,005
Emergency cesarean (%)	47,5	72,7	0,009
post-partum complication (%)	10,2	27,3	0,006
Exclusive breastfeeding (%)	66,9	39,4	0,232

Discussion:

Depressive Symptomatology

The average HADS-D score (8.5 ± 3.2) reflects mild to moderate depressive symptoms consistent with international prevalence estimates ranging from 10% to 25% in perinatal populations (7,16). Pregnancy represents a significant life event causing lasting biological, psychological, and social changes, with studies demonstrating an elevated risk for depression up to one year postpartum (17,18). Vulnerability factors include low self-esteem, social isolation, marital difficulties, and unintended pregnancy (19). Contrary to some findings associating younger maternal age with increased depression risk (20,21), this study did not find a significant effect of age. However, low educational attainment correlated with higher depressive symptoms, aligning with literature showing that

education enhances coping and health literacy (22). Economic hardship was significantly associated with greater depression severity, echoing findings from low-income settings (23). Unintended pregnancies were more prevalent among women with moderate to severe depression (24–26). Emergency cesarean delivery and postpartum complications were also significantly linked to higher depression scores, consistent with evidence highlighting their psychological burden (27–31). Exclusive breastfeeding showed a non-significant trend towards being less frequent among depressed women, in line with data suggesting oxytocin release during breastfeeding may protect against depression (29,32,33). The mean HADS-A score (8.8 ± 3.7) suggests mild to moderate anxiety, which is frequently underestimated in clinical settings (34). Anxiety symptoms may persist chronically beyond the postpartum period, often triggered or exacerbated by obstetric complications or traumatic birth experiences (35). Established risk factors include prior anxiety disorders, inadequate social support, and socioeconomic challenges (21,36). Prenatal anxiety adversely affects both pregnancy outcomes and child neurodevelopment (37). In this cohort, women living in rural areas had significantly higher anxiety prevalence, potentially due to reduced access to prenatal care and psychosocial support, consistent with prior Tunisian and South African studies (38,39). Higher educational levels appeared protective, improving pregnancy understanding and adaptive capacities (19,40,41). Unintended pregnancy and emergency cesarean sections were strongly associated with increased anxiety, corroborating meta-analytic evidence (26,27). Postpartum complications were also linked to sustained anxiety symptoms (31). Exclusive breastfeeding was less common among anxious women, which may disrupt the beneficial oxytocin-mediated anxiolytic effects of breastfeeding (36). This study presents several strengths. It explores the understudied domain of long-term perinatal mental health beyond the immediate postpartum phase. The use of the validated HADS scale ensures reliable assessment while minimizing confounding somatic symptoms. Online bilingual questionnaire dissemination enabled broader geographic and demographic reach within the Tunisian female population. Rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria reduced bias related to acute emotional states or pre-existing psychiatric conditions. Nevertheless, limitations exist. The small sample size restricts the generalizability of findings. Recruitment via social media and convenience sampling introduces selection bias. Self-administered questionnaires may be subject to self-report and social desirability biases. Finally, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences, underscoring the need for future longitudinal studies to elucidate temporal relationships between pregnancy and mental health outcomes.

Recommendations and Future Directions :

To mitigate perinatal anxiety and depression, systematic screening beyond the first three postpartum months is essential, particularly targeting women with low education, rural residence, unintended pregnancies, emergency cesarean deliveries, or postpartum complications. Strengthening the role of midwives, general practitioners, and community health workers through specialized training in perinatal mental health can enhance early detection and referral. Prolonged postnatal consultations incorporating psychological evaluation may improve comprehensive care and prevent late psychiatric complications. Engaging family and social networks, especially partners, in maternal psychological support, alongside public awareness campaigns on maternal mental health, is critical. Promoting breastfeeding, reducing social isolation, and enhancing access to mental health services—especially in rural areas—are key preventive measures. Longitudinal research is warranted to

monitor maternal mental health trajectories beyond the first postpartum year. Finally, national integrated perinatal mental health programs with interdisciplinary collaboration and patient-centered approaches should be developed to optimize care and outcomes.

Conclusion

Pregnancy and the postpartum period, extending beyond three months after delivery, represent critical phases during which women are susceptible to developing or experiencing worsening mental health conditions such as anxiety and depression. Our findings highlight key risk factors linked to elevated depressive and anxious symptoms, including low educational background, residence in rural areas, unintended pregnancies, emergency cesarean deliveries, and postpartum complications. These results emphasize that the psychological impact of motherhood can endure long after childbirth, significantly affecting maternal mental well-being. The fact that some women report their pregnancy as a source of anxiety stresses the importance of providing continuous and personalized psychosocial support. In response to these insights, it is essential to reinforce early detection efforts for maternal mental health disorders, ensure extended psychological monitoring during the postpartum period, and implement targeted interventions that consider socio-economic, cultural, and medical factors. Further multicenter longitudinal research is necessary to deepen understanding of maternal mental health trajectories and to assess the effectiveness of prevention and treatment approaches.

Declaration of Competing Interest:

The authors have no conflicts of interest relevant to this article.

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